

INNOVATION IN CATERING ESTABLISHMENTS: BENEFITS AND OBSTACLES

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Annotation. This article investigates the diagnosis of obstacles that prevent or hinder the introduction of innovations and the benefits of their implementation in improving the quality of public catering services in tourism and hotels.

Key words: Important factors, classification, innovation, international studies, Food service, world economy, business opportunities.

Introduction. Innovation is one of the important factors of increasing the competitiveness of enterprises. In the era of globalization and strong market competition, it is gaining importance with the continuous growth of customer and consumer demands. According to the researchers, among the businesses most affected by the crisis caused by the pandemic were companies in the tourism sector, namely travel agencies, accommodation companies, passenger transport companies and catering companies. In order to rapidly develop tourism as an important branch of the country's economy, extensive scientific research is being conducted aimed at radically improving the management of the tourism network, promoting them based on world market standards, and organizing high-quality catering services in tourism and their more innovative development.

Materials and method of research. Innovation is the driving force of the development of companies, taking into account new aspects that improve company processes [Szymanska, 2021]. The term "innovation" has an interdisciplinary character depending on the research perspective adopted [Carvalho and Costa, pp. 23-33]. The term "innovation" is derived from the Latin word "innovare" which translates as "to do something new" [Zawawi et al., 2016] or "innovatio" [Pałka-Łebek and Brambert, 2018]. In simple language, innovation means something new, different from current and previously used solutions and existing situation [Ober, 2022]. T. Kogbayew and A. Maziliauskas [2017] use this term to describe "the economic impact of technological change as the use of new combinations of existing production forces to solve business problems." Innovation is defined, including in documents and publications issued by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), as "a new or significantly improved product (product or service) or process, a new marketing method or economic practice, workplace organization or environment. a new organizational method in relations with [Oslo manual, 2018]. This definition is also adopted in this study.

It can be seen that the research carried out to date is related to the classification of innovation areas in tourism and the scope and impact of innovation, with special attention being paid to the determinants and sources of innovative ideas. Guidelines for the classification of different forms of innovation were developed by the authors of international studies conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in accordance with the Oslo guidelines [2005 and 2018].

Analysis and results. Food service is a complex activity that includes production, sales and service, and sometimes entertainment, aimed at the preparation and subsequent sale of culinary products for consumption, as well as creating conditions for their consumption. Public

catering enterprises are enterprises aimed at organizing the consumption of the offered products, primarily at the point of sale (as well as off-site) and providing other services to meet the needs of entertainment, recreation and mental recovery. Until 2019, general It should be noted that catering services are one of the most dynamic sectors in the world economy. However, this is a market that is very sensitive to any changes in the environment, including crisis situations. As a result of the pandemic, many restrictions were imposed on the catering chain, and its business opportunities were significantly limited. Companies operating in the sector had to take radical measures to continue their activities and survive this difficult situation. Innovation has become a necessity for entrepreneurs, not a choice.

The catering industry in our country is diversified both in terms of nature, quality and ownership. These are mostly sole traders, but others include global corporations [July 2022]. Systematization of public catering establishments used by the Central Statistics Office [GUS, 2023] and adopted in research work distinguishes the following categories: restaurants, bars, canteens and catering outlets. Restaurants are full-service dining establishments that feature a variety of menu items and beverages, as well as basic dining and entertainment options. provides. Bars are catering establishments that offer a smaller range than restaurants, usually limited to the most popular food products, often available as self-service (meals, snacks).

Most of the catering establishments in Uzbekistan are private (almost 99%). According to M. Sidorkievich and A. Tokarz [2011], the demand for catering services is mainly influenced by the wealth of the country's population.

As of February 1, 2024, the number of commercial enterprises operating in the catering sector is 25,294, of which the number of large enterprises is 80, and the number of small and micro-enterprises is 25,214.

Innovation in catering can bring a number of benefits, including:

- customer satisfaction, increased efficiency and higher profitability.
- By introducing new and creative menu items, caterers can attract a wider range of customers and retain more of their existing ones.
- Innovations in operations and technology can also streamline processes and reduce costs, leading to higher profitability in the long run.

At the same time, there are also barriers to innovation in catering establishments. These include:

- resistance to change by employees or management, concerns about the cost and time required to implement new ideas;
- includes lack of knowledge or experience with new technologies or trends;
- there may be regulatory barriers or industry norms that limit the ability of food businesses to experiment with new ideas.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that in order to overcome the barriers, catering companies can take active steps to increase the culture of innovation in their organizations. This includes encouraging employees to contribute their ideas and suggestions, investing in training and development programs to build skills in new technologies, and seeking partnerships or collaborations with external experts or organizations. possible By proactively seeking and embracing innovation, caterers can stay ahead of the competition and ensure their success in a rapidly evolving industry.

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